

ALPINE: A cLimbing robot for oPerations In mouNtain environmEnts

1st Michele Focchi
DISI, University of Trento
Trento, Italy
michele.focchi@unitn.it

2nd Andrea Del Prete
DISI, University of Trento
Trento, Italy
andrea.delprete@unitn.it

3rd Daniele Fontanelli
DII, University of Trento
Trento, Italy
daniele.fontanelli@unitn.it

3rd Luigi Palopoli
DISI, University of Trento
Trento, Italy
luigi.palopoli@unitn.it

Abstract—In this paper, we propose a robotic platform ALPINE able to move along very steep or vertical mountain slopes exploiting a combination of two ropes and a prismatic leg. The key contribution of the paper is a complete modelling of the system and a collection of preliminary results concerning motion planning.

Index Terms—Planning, Dynamic Modeling, Climbing Robots, Trajectory optimisation

I. INTRODUCTION

Mountain environments are extremely vulnerable to climate change and often subject to ruinous events such as landslides, floods and avalanches, which endanger a large number of economic activities (first and foremost tourism and agriculture) and put at risk the very survival of small towns and villages. Any realistic strategy to counter these risks is necessarily based on constant monitoring and on a thorough maintenance activity (e.g., to detach from the mountain walls dangerous boulders). However, the interested areas are often difficult to reach and operations are expensive and dangerous for human operators. From these considerations, we can derive an urgent need for a new generation of robots able to navigate along very steep mountain slopes in an efficient and repeatable way and perform complex tasks such as drilling holes, setting anchors in the rock, and scaling loose or dangerous boulders.

Climbing robots are robots able to move on vertical surfaces. They find application in many areas ranging from cleaning the glass windows of tall buildings, to maintaining and exploring wells and pipelines. Compared to other solutions like drone-based inspection [5] the use of climbing robots holds the promise to permit longer mission duration and more accurate operations. Walking-climbing robots [3] are often bio-inspired and have been popular for the last three decades. However, a critical reason why existing wall-climbing robots have not been available on the market is the risk of accidental fall due to operational failures (e.g., the feet could slip away from the slope in conditions of wet and irregular terrain) and the limited payload they can carry. Hybrid robots like Scamp demonstrated some perching abilities [4] using a propeller to stick to the wall or recover from a fall. Robots with rope access techniques [1] are considered a promising solution to address the payload issue. In addition, a rope can allow one to inspect a big area with limited means and remarkable speed.

Taking inspiration from human climbers and from our previous work [2], we propose a robotic platform called ALPINE able to move along very steep or vertical mountain slopes exploiting a combination of two ropes and of a prismatic leg that can be extended and retracted very quickly. The leg is used to make the robot jump by pushing it quickly away from the slope, while the rope is wound/unwound to control the vertical motion and the robot's trajectory during the flight phase.

This solution fulfils some requirements that are currently out of reach for conventional solutions:

R1: carry a heavy payload and maintain a stationary position for a long time without consuming energy (e.g., for maintenance operation); **R2:** move quickly and efficiently, **R3:** deal with irregular surface overcoming large obstacles along the way (bushes, rock formations); **R4:** execute autonomously/semi-autonomously a large number of on-site operations.

Our belief in our robot's ability to meet the constraints above is motivated by the following facts: 1. The rope allows the robot to carry heavy payloads and remain in a stationary position without consuming significant energy by engaging brakes (R1); 2. The combination of jumps and mixed vertical/lateral motions allows the robot to move quickly and efficiently (R2); 3. The application of optimal control strategies enables sophisticated motion planning strategies to fly over the slope most of the time and avoid irregularities and obstacles (R3); 4. The leg mechanism is designed to dissipate the excess of kinetic energy during the landing phase and to stay firmly attached to the surface to perform maintenance operations (R4).

The peculiarities of this platform (under-actuation, unilateral constraints, kinematic loops) lead to a number of scientific challenges that set the stage for ambitious research activities in both control and planning. The main contribution of this note is to provide a clear modelling framework and to outline our future agenda.

The paper is organised as follows. Section II-A presents the full kinematic model of the robot. In order to be able to plan trajectory in real-time, we derive in Section II-B a reduced-order model to be used in an optimal control setting. Finally, in Section III we present some preliminary planning results and validate the models.

Fig. 1. (left) Kinematic model of the ALPINE robot with two ropes. The landing links are attached to the side of the base and are deployed only at the landing.

II. ROBOT MODELING

A. Full detail model

Figure 1 illustrates the full detail model of the robot with two rope actuation. The robot consists of 3 kinematic chains branching from the base link. One is represented by the propulsion mechanism (a 3-DoFs prismatic robotic leg) [2]. At the extreme of the leg there is a point-like foot that enables to exert a *pure* Cartesian force (no moment) on the wall. The leg is also endowed with two rotational joints, that are used to align the leg to the thrusting impulse. This solution is to avoid *centroidal* moments that would pivot the robot around the rope axis. A prismatic knee joint is used to generate the *thrusting* impulse. The landing mechanism is represented by two additional rotational joints that move the landing links with two passive wheels at the extremes.

The other two kinematic chains are represented by the two ropes and their attachments. We model the attachment between each anchor and the rope by 2 *passive* (rotational) joints. The ropes can be seen as *actuated* prismatic joints followed by 3 *passive* rotational joints to model the connection between the rope and the *base link* of the robot.

B. Reduced order model

We model the system as a *point mass* (entirely concentrated in the body attached to the rope) under the action of the (unilateral) forces coming from the two ropes and the leg. We will make some additional assumptions: 1) the rope that is assumed to be in-extensible, rigid, and remains completely elongated (i.e., it cannot bend), 2) the re-winder mechanism can pull the rope when winding, but it cannot push (i.e., it can only act as a brake during the unwinding phase). Since we neglected the angular dynamics the number of degrees of freedom of the system is 3.

The ropes introduce a holonomic constraint that captures the fact that the distance between the rope attachment points and the base link is constant. This constraint can be also expressed at the velocity/acceleration level becoming a Pfaffian constraint. This holonomic constraint creates a loop in the

Fig. 2. Simplified model with two anchor points. The inertial (\mathcal{W}) frame is attached to the left anchor frame.

kinematics and we will enforce it explicitly by adopting a redundant representation (5 DoFs) of the system configuration, choosing as generalised coordinates for our model the Cartesian position $\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ of the mass and the lengths $l_1 \in \mathbb{R}$, $l_2 \in \mathbb{R}$ of the two ropes:

$$\mathbf{q} = [\mathbf{p}^T \quad l_1 \quad l_2]^T \in \mathbb{R}^5 \quad (1)$$

for a point mass, from the Newton Equation we have:

$$m\ddot{\mathbf{p}} - m\mathbf{g} = \hat{\mathbf{f}}_{r,1}F_{r,1} + \hat{\mathbf{f}}_{r,2}F_{r,2} + \mathbf{F}_{leg} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{p}_{a,1}$, $\mathbf{p}_{a,2}$, are the two anchor point positions, $\hat{\mathbf{f}}_{r,i} = \frac{\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_{a,i}}{\|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_{a,i}\|} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and $F_{r,i} \in \mathbb{R}$ are the rope axis and the magnitudes of the forces exerted by the ropes, respectively, with $i = \{1, 2\}$. $\mathbf{F}_{leg} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the impulsive force generated by the leg. By enforcing the following two scalar constraints, the total number of degrees of freedom reduces to 3:

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_{a,1})^T (\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_{a,1}) &= l_1^2 \\ (\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_{a,2})^T (\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_{a,2}) &= l_2^2 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

for the integration of the dynamics it is convenient to express these constraints at the acceleration level:

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_{a,1})^T \ddot{\mathbf{p}} + \dot{p}^2 &= \dot{l}_1^2 + l_1 \ddot{l}_1 \\ (\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_{a,2})^T \ddot{\mathbf{p}} + \dot{p}^2 &= \dot{l}_2^2 + l_2 \ddot{l}_2 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Then, we can isolate the accelerations to get the differential equations of the dynamics, in the following matrix form:

$$\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} mI_{3 \times 3} & 0 & 0 \\ (\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_{a,1})^T & -l_1 & 0 \\ (\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_{a,2})^T & 0 & -l_2 \end{bmatrix}}_A \begin{bmatrix} \ddot{\mathbf{p}} \\ \ddot{l}_1 \\ \ddot{l}_2 \end{bmatrix} = \quad (5)$$

$$\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} m\mathbf{g} + (\hat{\mathbf{f}}_{r,1}F_{r,1} + \hat{\mathbf{f}}_{r,2}F_{r,2} + \mathbf{F}_{leg}) \\ \dot{l}_1^2 - \dot{p}^2 \\ \dot{l}_2^2 - \dot{p}^2 \end{bmatrix}}_b \quad (6)$$

Fig. 3. Planned trajectory for the validation jump test.

from which we get, the relationship between forces and accelerations, for the defined chosen coordinates:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \ddot{p} \\ \ddot{l}_1 \\ \ddot{l}_2 \end{bmatrix} = A^{-1}b \quad (7)$$

Remarkably, this model is singularity-free.

III. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

In this section, we report some preliminary results of planning jumping trajectories via a single shooting optimal control approach making use of the model (7). In the first experiment, we ran the optimisation to perform a 16 m long jump starting from an initial position $\mathbf{p}_0 = [0.22 \ 2.5 \ -6]^T$ to a higher/lateral target at $\mathbf{p}_f = [0.22 \ 4 \ -4]^T$ [m] (see Fig. 3).

We validate the results of the optimization for both the simplified model (in a Matlab environment) and the full 3D model (see Fig. 1). In this case, we built a Gazebo simulator based on the URDF description of the robot. For the Matlab simulation, we simply integrated (7) with an ode45 Runge-Kutta variable-step scheme. For the Gazebo simulation, we assumed to apply the push impulse as a force $\mathbf{F}_c \in \mathbb{R}^3$ at the contact point mapping the centroidal force \mathbf{F}_{leg} obtained from the optimisation at the foot level.

Figure 4 reports the tracking of the robot Cartesian position and the pattern of the forces applied to the ropes to achieve the target. It is interesting to note how the optimization managed to circumvent the maximum limit set for the rope force ($F_{r,max} = -90N$), taking a longer jump with initial downward phase. Analyzing the first 3 plots we can evince that the norm of the error at the touch-down is below 5 cm (0.35% of the jump length) and is mainly due to integration drifts, while in the full-model Gazebo simulation is around 50 cm (3% of jump length). This is due to a number of reasons: 1) the control inputs are applied in open-loop, therefore any uncertainty causes an error in the lift-off momentum that can cause drift during the jump, 2) the approximations due to the simplified model with respect to the full one used in the Gazebo simulation.

Fig. 4. Simulation. Validation of the optimized trajectory. The red line is the CoM trajectory computed by the optimization. The blue and black lines are the simulated trajectories with Matlab and Gazebo, respectively. The plot at the bottom represents the rope retraction forces $F_{r,1}(t), F_{r,2}(t)$.

However, a 3% error is in a range that can be efficiently coped with a controller, which is part of future works, and shows that the simplified model is a good approximation for the real system. Indeed, the highest error is on the direction X which is always closer to be perpendicular to the rope plane, where the system under-actuation is more prominent. Adding propellers to the back of the base (see Fig. 1) could enhance the controllability in this direction. Finally, in the accompanying video¹ we present multiple jumps for a number of targets equally spaced in an ellipsoid around \mathbf{p}_0 .

In conclusion, we presented a robotic platform ALPINE that can perform multiple jumps on a vertical/slanted surface. A reduced order (point mass) model turned out to be sufficient to successfully find optimized solutions for multiple jumps that do not involve angular motions. In our future work, we will focus on improving the model (7) to achieve faster convergence of the optimisation, increasing its descriptiveness (i.e. considering the angular dynamics) in order to plan jumps with significant reorientation of the platform.

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¹Video link: <https://youtu.be/ETZjINBTIJY>